

STATICAL DATA ON ACUTE LYMPHOBLASTIC LEUKEMIA IN CHILDREN

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Abstract: Every year in developed countries, acute lymphoblastic leukemia (ALL) affects an average of 40-45 children per 1 million, the incidence of acute myeloid leukemia (AML) averages 7 children per 1 million children.

Keywords: leukemia, analysis, stage, syndrome, acute

Leukemias are a heterogeneous group of malignant clonal diseases of the hematopoietic tissue, belonging to the group of hemoblastoses. In typical cases, OL is characterized by a combination of anemic and intoxication symptom complex, proliferative and hemorrhagic syndromes. In OnLL, proliferative syndromes are less common than in ALL, but intoxication, anemic and hemorrhagic syndromes, damage to the central nervous system, bones, gingival hypertrophy, and hyperleukocytes are more frequent. Acute promyelocytic leukemia is characterized by DIC with severe bleeding.

Purpose of the study. To analyze the clinical picture of the disease at the time of the initial treatment; identify the most characteristic and common symptoms of ALL in the early stages of diagnosis.

Methodology. The data of randomly selected outpatient medical records of 63 children under the supervision of a hematologist of the Urgensk city children's polyclinic for ALL diagnosed in the period from 2007 to 2017 were studied. the number of cases of AML in the Khorezm region during the specified period of time (3 cases). Information regarding the initial treatment and diagnosis of the disease was taken into account, including complaints, data from physical, laboratory and instrumental studies available to the local pediatrician. Simple statistics are used.

Research results. In the study group, there were slightly more girls than boys (47.1 and 52.7%, respectively). Most often, the disease was detected at preschool age 4-8 years - in 17 people (47.2%). There were slightly fewer cases in early childhood 1-3 years - 16 cases (45%). The most rare cases were children with ALL manifestation at senior school age - 3 cases (8.5%). The clinical symptoms of AL depend on the degree of inhibition of normal hematopoiesis and the severity of extramedullary manifestations.

Symptoms of the extended period of the disease are grouped into the following main syndromes: hyperplastic or proliferative, hemorrhagic, anemic, osteoarticular, intoxication, immunodeficiency [3]. Hyperplastic syndrome is

characterized by painless enlargement of the lymph nodes, liver and spleen. Lymph nodes have a dense texture, painless, mobile, not soldered to each other and the surrounding tissues

In some, the lymph nodes were expressed everywhere, ranging in size from 1.0x2.0 to 3.0x4.0 cm, in others, isolated conglomerates were found in the cervical, inguinal, axillary regions - 4 cases (9.8%). Most often were enlarged cervical in 26 children. (63.4%), axillary in 20 (48.8%) and inguinal in 19 children. (46.3%) lymph nodes. All groups of palpable lymph nodes were enlarged in 6 children (19.4%); 2-5 groups - 20 (48.8%); 1 group - 4 people. (9.8%), and in 3 of 4 cases, the inguinal lymph nodes were enlarged.

The absence of enlargement of the lymph nodes was observed in 2 cases (4.9%), however, in one of them, the reaction of the lymphoid tissue took place in the form of enlargement and loosening of the tonsils; an increase in the tonsils was observed in 2 more cases. Gingival hyperplasia and ulcerative necrotic stomatitis, characteristic of the hyperplastic syndrome, are observed in the severe course of the process and are regarded as an unfavorable prognostic sign

